

Samten Hills Dalat

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While Samten Hills is certainly a religious place -- arguably the most lavish Tibetan Buddhist temple complex in Vietnam -- there is a definitional ambiguity that makes it difficult to nail down. Simply put, Samten Hills means different things to different people. At the most basic, Samten Hills is a luxury tourist resort that promises 'Relax. Reflect. Renew' (according to the motto). It is built on rolling hills outside of Đà Lạt city in the Central Highlands, an area known for romantic nature (due to French colonial hill stations and local ethnic minority groups) and spiritual power emanating from the mountains. Samten Hills has high-end villas, restaurants, cafes and shops, along with hundreds of campsites for those seeking a more rustic experience. In that sense, it is a for-profit business. However, the 'heart of Samten Hills' is Samten Ling, a Tibetan Buddhist temple operated by monks from the Drikung Kagyu lineage. Those monks come mostly from Lamayuru Temple in Ladakh (India). As a temple, Samten Ling has a resident rinpoche (Sonam Jorphen Rinpoche), monks and various attendants. Beginning in February 2023, during a 2-week inauguration, they hosted many Vajrayana empowerments. Samten Ling is also home to some large religious objects, including Tibetan Buddhist statues and the newly-minted Guinness record world's largest gold-plated prayer wheel. The ambiguity is about terminology: some people consider Samten Hills to be a tourist business that facilitates the temple; others consider it to be a temple that entices tourism. Officially, Samten Hills is (allegedly) registered as a business or heritage museum. As a Vajrayana place, is not registered as a temple within the officially government recognized Vietnam Buddhist Sangha. It is sometimes officially called a "spiritual and cultural space for Vajrayana Buddhism in Vietnam" and a "cultural and spiritual center Samten Hills." The polysemy of Samten Hills has only intensified since the completion of the March 2023 inauguration, as the place has come under official investigation for functioning as a religious place (allegedly) against the stated purpose of the land agreement, which was framed within "forestation and management, grass planting and dairy farming, in combination with cultural and touristic experiences at Tu Tra commune." This entry is based on fieldwork at Samten Hills during the Inauguration period and interviews with over 60 Vajrayana followers and Samten Hills employees.

Date Range: 2023 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Đà Lạt

Region tags: Asia, Vietnam, Central Vietnam

Samten Hills Dalat is located in Kambute hamlet, Tutra commune, Đơn Dương district, Đà Lạt city, Lâm Đồng province.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: "Entrance to Faith: Biography of Kyabje Drubwang Sonam Jorfel Rinpoche" by Lopon Konchok Samphel, translated by Sonam Spitz and edited by Ryan Bolye
- Source 3: <https://samtenhills.vn/en/>

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M8EFZrEpUdE>
- Source 1 Description: Official video highlighting architecture.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R6u_N2PKPZI
- Source 2 Description: Cultural performance inside temple during Inauguration.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lzEc4h9z7Kk>
- Source 3 Description: Inauguration of the world's largest prayer wheel.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ccrs.ku.dk/research/centres/centre-for-contemporary-buddhist-studies/blog/buddhist-resorts-and-guinness-records-in-vietnams-central-highlands/>
- Source 1 Description: Blog written by the authors about Samten Hills
- Source 2 URL: <https://laodong.vn/xa-hoi/samten-hills-da-lat-khong-phai-khu-tam-linh-ton-giao-1181354.lido>
- Source 2 Description: News article on Samten Hills investigation

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Hill
- Other [specify]: Samten Hills is in the Central Highlands, outside Đà Lạt city, in an area that is known for spiritual tourism.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Water feature

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: The land was cleared, levelled and various artificial water areas and plants are now part of the landscape.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Samten Hills is located near the very small population area of Kambute, Tutra Commune, in Đơn Dương District.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: There are several features.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The temple construction was done by Ladakhi craftsmen and is part of an overall Tibetan Vajrayana aesthetic that permeates the whole resort.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The design is modernist Tibetan Buddhism.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Samten Hills was donated by (somewhat) anonymous sponsors and includes a large area. It is unified by the idea of Samten Hills but in the future may include a 2,000 student Buddhist university.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: It is the site of many empowerments.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: Samten Hills is effectively finished and has been inaugurated in February-March 2023. It is now functioning, although the current investigation for hosting religious events has created some ambiguity about its operations. While the essential aspects of Samten Ling are complete -- the statues, iconography, temples and prayer wheel -- there is future planning for a Buddhist university that would create bilateral agreements between Vietnam and India.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Not dedicated to a specific being, but dedicated as a functioning temple and residence for monks from the Drikung Kagyu lineage of Tibetan Buddhism. The lineage began in 11th century with the great translator, Marpa (for more information, see <https://www.drikung.org/>). Many supernatural deities are present in the temple iconography and are addressed through ritual action like empowerments.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Chakrasambara is the signature empowerment of Drikung Kagyu and for inaugurating new temples

– Yes [specify]: Chakrasambara is the signature empowerment of Drikung Kagyu and for inaugurating new temples. However, the temple is not dedicated to or based on a specific yidam.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Several bodhisattvas and enlightened teachers (including Chetsang Rinpoche and Sonam Jorfel Rinpoche) are given places of prominence.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Samten Hills was funded by (semi) anonymous Vietnamese donors, constructed according to the specifications of Tibetan Buddhism by Indian craftsmen, and granted a building permit and partial (contested) recognition by the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha and local government officials at Lâm Đồng Province.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: While some supernatural instruction came from Sonam Jorphel Rinpoche, Samten Hills was built by a combination of Vietnamese laborers and skilled craftsmen from India who are versed in Vajrayana temple construction.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: Although there are many spiritual stories about the selection of the place.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: One of the donors was a long-time member of Drikung Kagyu in Da Lat. While not a singular event, the association (and other spiritual signs) led to the creation of Samten Hills.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The sponsor is semi private -- while she gave an Inauguration Day speech to thousands of people, she was not introduced as 'the sponsor' of Samten Hills. Suffice to say that she is a follower of Drikung Kagyu.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: See notes.

Notes: This depends on who you ask. If you look holistically at the resort-cum-temple, and all its associated branding and marketing, there is a clear financial aspect that creates an expectation for financial returns. However, many people may be motivated by the desire to spread Vajrayana Dharma in Vietnam and to benefit all sentient beings -- an act more driven by devotion than expectation. We are currently writing three articles on the motivations for supporting Vajrayana, especially among elite, young, urban followers, as opposed to patronizing established Vietnamese Mahayana traditions.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: As described in the introduction, there are many ideas of Samten Hills -- as a resort, business, temple, cultural space, Vajrayana site -- and the original design and purpose of Samten Hills depends on who one talks to. Some may emphasize the housing of important religious objects from Tibetan Buddhism.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The entire concept is based on fusion of natural and human-made structures. For example, The Leaf Coffeeshop is modelled on foliage.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The golden bridge supported by human hands, ending with a statue of Maitreya Buddha, is attached to the main Samten Ling temple.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Notes: Although for tourism purposes the Guinness record world's largest prayer wheel has become the iconic structure of Samten Hills.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are several monumental statues and the prayer wheel. We are uncertain what percentage of land this takes up given the vast land holding of Samten Hills. Perhaps less than 2% of the total size.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 16.53

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 37.22

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: copper, gold

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: concrete

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Vajrayana iconography is a vital aspect of Samten Hills. In contrast to some other Vajrayana sites in Vietnam that fuse tourism with spirituality, Samten Hills has delicate, hand-painted decorations done by Ladakhi artisans.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Various decorations are detachable, such as Tibetan tent structures.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: To see the inside of the temple and the various deities represented (Guru Rinpoche, Zambala, Taras and so on), please see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TVu0-dsMOsw>.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: For example, mandalas.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The range of Vajrayana depictions are typical of other temple structures in Tibet and South Asia. It is notable that there is no architectural or iconographic hybridity at Samten Hills (in distinction to other Tibetan Buddhist structures in Vietnam).

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Some thangkas and statues are covered or placed in private inside settings.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The largest is the Maitreya statue (10.5 meters) and Amitayus Buddha.

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Smaller statues are throughout the property.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: For example, kirtimukha guardians, naga snakes, and other reliefs like on the prayer wheel.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Smaller reliefs like decorative features are present.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings and thangkas are extraordinary inside Samten Ling. They are done in iconographic measurements and are not hybridized with Sino-Vietnamese features, as seen in some other temples.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Smaller paintings are present as well.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The most prominent inscriptions are informative -- describing the Vietnam Federation of UNESCO Associations recognition and Guinness records. See <http://unescovietnam.vn/>.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Smaller inscriptions may be present.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Typical decorations found in other Tibetan Buddhist temples around the world.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: It is notable that the iconography is done according to exact specifications as seen in Ladakh and other Tibetan cultural areas. The lack of distinct features is broadly different from other Vajrayana sites in Vietnam, which may be hybridized.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Many visitors and tourists felt that Samten Hills is filled with positive magnetic energy from the spiritual constructions (of the temple, prayer wheel, and buddha statues), the presence of venerable Vajrayana monks, and the series of empowerments given during the 2-week inauguration. Many people claimed to have better sleep and meditation during the time staying here. Tinna Tinh, the Vajrayana key opinion leader (KOL), produced multiple video blogs on Youtube, sharing her personal experiences and connection with the divine land of Samten Hills. Ms. Tinh was showcased in the cultural festival and is an integral part of popularizing Samten Hills in her position as a social media personality with close ties to Vajrayana.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: During the inauguration event, Drikung Kyabgon Chetsang Rinpoche, the 37th spiritual leader of the Drikung Kagyu lineage gave a three-day Chakrasamvara empowerment. Chakrasamvara is considered one of the most prominent deity with the Kagyu lineage. After the first day of the empowerment, blessed hay was distributed to everyone to put under their pillow and mattress for dream watching. A good dream is a green flag for receiving the empowerment on the second day. A bad dream is a spiritual warning that this empowerment is not appropriate for the person to receive and practice.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Visualization is a core practice of Tibetan Buddhism that requires the practitioners to project themselves as the deities, in turn results in a similar experience of being possessed. Visualization is a crucial component in Vajrayana empowerments.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Communication with the deities can be facilitated and established directly through visualization, not exclusively through high-level religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: We have collected several personal accounts of visitors reported feeling the presence of dead spirits at Samten Hills, possibly from wartime.

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

– No

Notes: Although we talked to visitors who felt energy from fallen soldiers on the land.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on the individual experience of those who attend. Some felt non-human supernatural beings.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– No

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitoring comes in different forms. Formally, karmic cause and effect are operative. Informally, followers may have individual senses of how supernatural beings protect over them, watch them, and care about their actions. While Tibetan Buddhism does not put a heavy emphasis on a sexual code of conduct, and Drikung Kagyu is no exception, inside Samten Hills there are rules prohibiting sex and intoxicants.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: tsok

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: tsok

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

Notes: There are rules for staying at Samten Hills, including maintaining ritual behaviour and not having sex or taking intoxicants.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: These communications can come through empowerments, meditation, ritual practices, and dreams.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings are typical of Vajrayana temples. Tsok blessings may be daily objects like juice boxes and cookies. However, donations in envelopes may constitute large financial donations.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Other material offerings may be present.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: The maintenance is divided between Samten Hills secular staff (who do landscaping, customer service, restaurant work) and the resident monks (who do ritual cleansing of the temple grounds).

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Not formal pilgrimage, although in interviews with visitors to the Inauguration events it was obvious that for many people the trip to Đà Lạt (which is about six hours from Hồ Chí Minh City by car) constituted a kind of pilgrimage in itself.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests
– Yes

↳ Local elites
– Yes

↳ Private contributions
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
– Yes [specify]: There are several restaurants and a couple of large tented overhangs for eating.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: After the Inauguration, it is unclear if specific festivals will be held at Samten Hills, although it would fit with the marketing scheme.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:
Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species
– No

↳ Divination through human communication:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:

–Oil

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Clearly, some empowerments are directed at healing, wealth and long life. Divination is a common feature of Vajrayana temples. We saw examples of this in more informal settings.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Expiation

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Large scale rituals include empowerments that can have many people (spilling out of the temple and into the hanger with a jumbo screen). Small scale rituals can include individuals walking the kora (12 minutes per round).

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 300

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: During the inauguration, everyday.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Red wine is blessed during empowerments and distributed in small teaspoons to attendants.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Only men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Most are Tibetan or Indian (Ladakhi) and at least one monk is from the USA.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, although this depends on the ongoing investigation and also the wishes of Sonam Jorphel Rinpoche.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Samten Ling is typical in the hierarchical achievements of individual monks.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: In the seating arrangement and the order to approach the dias for blessings.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: There are dorms and villas for the resident monks.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: And also conferring status on religious specialists based on their achievement.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Samten Hills as a for-profit resort company operates the maintenance of the wider resort. Samten Ling temple complex is inside of it.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: Temple administration runs like any Tibetan temple, with the important caveat that in Vietnam there are late-Socialist regulations on religious freedom.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Samten Hills leadership has not officially shared information about their business model.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: We are not sure about leasing agreements that Samten Hills has with Lâm Đồng Province. However, small-scale businesses (like food trucks and shops) are operating both inside and adjacent to Samten Hills.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: During the Inauguration ceremonies, daily free lunch and water was provided to everyone. Going forward, now Samten Hills charges an entrance fee.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Samten Hills bottles its own water.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: It is accessible by road.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Samten Hills feels that it emits spiritual energy that benefits Lâm Đồng Province in particular and all sentient beings in general.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No